

WORD COMPRESSION - AS A WIDELY USED METHOD OF OCCASIONAL REARRANGEMENT OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Annotation: The article deals with the method of occasional rearrangement of phraseological units. In world linguistics, more and more attention is paid to the research of phraseological units based on the concept of semantic field. Researching the structure of the phraseological units representing atmospheric phenomena and the relationship between the units within the semantic field reveals the unique aspects of each language and makes it possible to determine its theoretical foundations. Taking into account the polysemous words formed by the word "Wind" from the point of view of the types of connections between their meanings showed that there are two types of connections between the meanings in the semantic structures of the studied phraseological units - subordinate and equal connections.

Key words: phraseological unit, insertion, lexico-semantic group, inclusion, semantic group, stable combination, emotive.

Introduction. Adding variable elements to the structure of phraseological units is one of the most common forms of changing phraseological units. Word compression is considered by many linguists as a widely used method of occasional rearrangement of phraseological units.

Method of the Research. Phraseological identification method, comparison method, descriptive, statistical, component analysis and transformation methods were used.

Discussion and Results. The essence and linguistic nature of word compression is most fully covered in the work of A.V. Kunin.

We proceed from the rules set out in the work cited in our analysis of word compression.

The insertion of variable elements into the content of phraseological unit is aimed at clarifying, strengthening or weakening its meaning.

We examine this occasional method with the aim of clarifying, strengthening or weakening the meaning of the phraseological unit or not by clarifying, strengthening or weakening the meaning of the LSG (lexico-semantic group) contained in the phraseological unit.

The research material shows that clarification of the meaning of phraseological unit occurs under the influence of the inclusion of adverbs and adjectives, adjectives, pronouns, introductory sentences.

We turn to examples:

“wear an air”

1. *Edna returned, looking her usual self except that she wore a slightly tragic air.* (J.B.Priestley. Angel Pavement. – P. 229)

“trim one’s sails to the wind”

2. *The Cecils were seriously alarmed, and Burghley trimming his sails to the changing wind, thought it advisable at the next Council to take the side of Essex in the matter of the Spanish ransoms.* (L.Strachey. Elizabeth and Essex. - P. 103)

“under a cloud”

3. No, hardly, that. But I’ve lived all my life under that cloud. Could I get into the Philadelphia club? (J.O’Hara. The Lockwood Concern. – P. 130)

“trim one’s sails to the wind”

4. *Mr. Hoover, in his address announcing his acceptance of the republican nomination and declaring his general policy, has trimmed his sails with what we suspect to be good judgement of the wind.* (The Economist, August 20, 1932)

In all the examples given, the added variable elements not only clarify the re-conceived meaning of the phraseological unit, but also contribute to the revitalization of the refined image of the phraseological unit by concretizing the meanings of the LSG components in the given phraseological units with various determiners. The addition of words differs from the others in the first example in that the meaning of the phraseological unit clarified by the compression of the "tragic" quality at the same time leads to some weakening with the help of the addition of the adverb "slightly", that is, in this example, our work falls into a combined situation of two tasks - clarifying and weakening the meaning of the phraseological unit. In the last example, the introductory sentence "with what we suspect to be good judgment" is inserted into the content of the phraseological unit, which shows the author's comment. The fact that the input refers to the "wind" component is not accidental - it is the "wind" component that reports the image that has already existed on phraseological unit. In its own way, this shortened word becomes a cliché, gives phraseological unit a new meaning, and the whole discussion acquires an expressive color.

The most common form of word adding is word compression to enhance the meaning of phraseological unit. They are divided into:

1. Compression of an adjective.

“like the wind”

But it didn't help her, she felt a force driving her on like a strong wind pressing on her shoulder blades and she couldn't turn her head to look back. (J.Lindsay. Betrayed Spring. – P. 497)

In the given example, the introduction of the quality "strong" serves to strengthen the meaning of the phraseological unit. Strengthening the meaning of phraseological unit comes from the need to update it. In the process of use, this phraseological unit was "squeezed" and there was a need to further strengthen its meaning, which in this case was achieved by compressing the "strong" quality.

2. Adding an adverb.

Proper scared they were to see a vessel without sails or oars, going right straight ahead, nine knots an hour, in the very wind's eye. (J.Aldridge. The Sea Eagle. – P. 67)

As in the previous case, the insertion of the adverb "very" helps to reinforce the meaning of the phraseological unit as a whole.

3. Adding stable combinations.

"to ride out (weather) the storm"

Sybil sighed. "I'm very happy sitting here with my husband and my friends. I feel we've weathered one hell of a storm." (J. Braine. *Life at the Top*. – P. 124)

In a stable combination, the contraction of "a hell of" increases the meaning of the phraseological unit, and in addition, an emotional tone arises in the FU. Emotional overtones are so consequential that the stable conjunction "a hell of" itself belongs to the emotive discharge. When embedded in the phraseological unit, it transfers its emotional power to the entire phraseological unit.

4. Adding of two adjectives and adverbs.

"to give the air to somebody"

Another way is to give Nato a more political and less narrowly defensive air. (The Economist, June 18, 1966)

First of all, the unconnected structure of the phraseological unit attracts the reader's attention. The linear arrangement of the components is broken by the compression of the two qualities and the approach. As a result of the remote location of the components, the expressiveness of the message increases significantly.

The given example represents the combination of two adjectives that combine to strengthen and clarify the meaning, and at the same time narrow it down with the help of the adverb "narrowly". The vividness of the reasoning is further aided by the comparative use of both adjectives.

The comparison of an occasionally renewed phraseological unit with its linguistic counterpart further strengthens the stylistic meaning of FB, its expressiveness due to the revival of the metaphor.

5. Adding three qualities.

"to ride out (weather) the storm"

She was a housewife of experience who had weathered the most fantastic tropical domestic storms in Singapore. (J. B. Priestley. *Angel Pavement*. – P. 111)

In this example, three adjectives are embedded in the FU, the first of which amplifies the meaning of the phraseological unit, and the other two clarify it. The strengthening of the denotative meaning of phraseological unit occurs due to the interaction of the lexical meaning of the word "fantastic" with the grammatical meaning of the high level of quality.

Phraseological units formed with the members of the lexical semantic group under consideration are also characterized by their inclusion of various variable elements.

Let's look at the following examples.

"to ride out (weather) the storm"

1. *But for the war and the upset of every one's mind and life and character, it might have weathered the small storms of Fanny and the young man – and perhaps other Fannies and other young men – and still have gone on working.* (R. Aldington. *Death of a Hero*. – P. 190)

"to be winded"

2. *Lydia called out to the audience: "Give us a minute, friends. Comrage Turner just ran two hundred miles from Reata – he's a little winded."* (L. Lawrence. *Old Father Antic*. – P. 256)

"to live on air"

3. *The very same, "replied the mistress of the hotel, with a piteous aspect of woe", "a gentle baste and one that could and did live on less than air", at need.* (J. F. Cooper. *The Spy*. – P. 145)

"to take wind"

4. *Keep this wooing secret, if it takes the least wind, old Moody will be sure to hinder it.* (Dryden. New Composition IV)

“like lightning”

5. *Her fear flickered like weak lightning in the neutral space between them.* (J.Wain.A. Winter in the Hills. – P. 119)

In all given examples, the insertion of various variable elements into a phraseological unit activates the "small", "smaller", "smallest", "weakest" themes in the speech, which weaken the meaning of the phraseological unit. This is possible due to the fact that the members of the lexical semantic group "storm", "wind", "air", "lightning" retain part of their semantics in independent use, while they help each other with the meaning of the compressed elements, the meaning becomes more alive.

Conclusion. Weakening of the meanings of the analyzed phraseological units is related to the semantics of phraseological units, and there is a need to weaken them in the context in order to make their meaning more pleasant.

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